

Face Recognition Based Automatic Attendance Management System

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Abstract— The aim of this study is to develop a face based automated attendance system for hostels, utilizing facial recognition technology based on the K-nearest neighbors (KNN) algorithm. One goal is to minimize the need for direct human involvement when keeping track of attendance, as this task can be arduous, time-consuming, and resource-intensive (such as when relying on manual methods that use paper). However, we do not aim to completely eliminate human interactions from this process. To improve efficiency, the proposed approach reduces the need for manual attendance recording and management. By incorporating modern technology, the system significantly reduces resource requirements while improving accuracy and reliability. The use of facial recognition technology has gained popularity in attendance management due to its ability to enhance multimedia information access and strengthen network security. The proposed system utilizes Python for image processing, feature extraction, and matching, resulting in improved human-computer interface and better system usability. Overall, the KNN algorithm provides an effective solution for face recognition in attendance management and contributes to the advancement of automated attendance systems.

Keywords—Automated attendance system, K-nearest neighbor algorithm, facial recognition, Image processing, Feature extraction and matching, Python

I. INTRODUCTION

Managing attendance is a crucial task for educational institutions like schools, colleges, and hostels. Nevertheless, the management of attendance by manual methods can be a laborious process and susceptible to inaccurate recordings. One probable resolution to the aforementioned difficulties involves the implementation of facial recognition technology. We propose a face recognition-based attendance management system for hostels that employs the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm. The system uses a camera-based attendance system to capture students' facial features as they enter or exit the hostel premises. The KNN algorithm compares these images with a pre-existing database of student images to recognize individuals and mark their attendance. The proposed system provides real-time updates on attendance records and generates accurate timesheets for each student.

This system has several benefits, such as reduced manual errors, savings in time and resources, and the ability to

integrate with other HRMS or payroll systems. The KNN algorithm ensures accurate recognition of individuals, even in low-light conditions, and is easily adaptable to changes in the student population.

In summary, this paper introduces a reliable, efficient, and accurate face recognition-based attendance management system that can significantly reduce the workload of hostel administrators and provide an automated and convenient solution to attendance management. The use of face recognition technology offers several benefits in attendance management systems some of which are given below.

- Reduces the likelihood of manual errors, enhancing accuracy.
- Saves time and resources by eliminating the need for manual attendance marking.
- Integration with other HRMS or payroll systems is straightforward.
- Time and date formats can be customized to meet organizational needs.
- AI-powered attendance systems are more automated and maintain real-time daily records.
- Generates precise timesheets for individual students on a large scale.

Challenges :

i) Data Preprocessing: The quality of the input images is crucial for face detection and recognition. Images with poor quality, such as low resolution, occlusion, and illumination variation, may reduce the accuracy of the KNN algorithm.

ii) Feature Extraction: Feature extraction is the process of selecting relevant features that represent the facial image. The KNN algorithm requires a feature extraction step to convert the images into numerical data that can be used for classification. Choosing appropriate features can be challenging, especially when dealing with large datasets.

iii) Class Imbalance: In attendance management systems, the number of images for each person may not be equal, leading to class imbalance. This imbalance can affect the performance of the KNN algorithm as it tends to favor the majority class.

iv) Scalability: The K-nearest neighbor (KNN) algorithm is a memory-dependent approach that mandates the storage of all training information in memory. As the volume of images in the database increases, the algorithm's memory demands also

escalate, posing a challenge in extending the system's scalability to handle sizable datasets.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The main aim of this article is to examine in-depth the central objective of the review of various approaches proposed by other researchers and assess the strengths and weaknesses of their methodologies. The identification and subsequent selection of the optimal course of action for implementation will rely upon a thorough investigation and assessment of all viable alternatives.

In reference [1], the author introduces the idea of utilizing facial recognition to mark students' attendance. The proposed methodology involves the implementation of Principal Component Analysis and local binary pattern. Nonetheless, there are lingering concerns regarding the accuracy and effectiveness of the system's facial recognition capability. To address this issue in the future, researchers plan to adopt a more advanced approach by combining rapid PCA with back-propagation.

In reference [2], the authors describe a novel approach that relies on the Histogram of Oriented Gradients technique and incorporates Firebase to store attendance-related information. The facial recognition algorithm's accuracy was assessed at 99.38 percent for the labeled faces.

The proposed approach by the authors of [3] suggested a face recognition algorithm based on Eigenvector and Eigenvalue. Here they faced problems when the threshold value was less than the calculated value.

Reference [4] presents a system that utilizes two software applications, namely MATLAB and Microsoft Excel, and a personal computer (PC) to facilitate the attendance recording process. The researchers ensured that the camera driver was appropriately installed and compatible with MATLAB before capturing images or videos. The system cropped the faces in the images to identify individuals and then compared them with the existing face database. Upon successful recognition of a face, the system recorded attendance in an Excel spreadsheet.

Reference [5] outlines a methodology that employs Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) for facial recognition purposes. The system's unique approach involves combining the YOLO V3 algorithm with the Azure Face API, enabling real-time attendance recording, which enhances accuracy and saves time.

In reference [6], the authors introduce a novel attendance management system that employs facial recognition technology. The system is designed to provide students with accurate attendance information in a user-friendly format. Data transmission to the server is achieved through an Ethernet cable. The system's user interface is highly intuitive and easy to navigate, while also incorporating robust security measures. Additionally, the system has the ability to generate

comprehensive reports on student attendance and can also send notifications to proctors and parents in the event of any absences.

In [7] the authors proposed automated attendance management system utilizes the LBPH algorithm for face recognition and haar-cascades for face detection. Its functionalities involve capturing pictures of students, saving their information in a database, training the images on the camera and database, and monitoring the entry of individuals into the classroom. Upon entering the classroom, the system processes the faces from the camera and performs pre-processing for further analysis.

The authors in [8] utilized the Viola and Jones algorithm to generate bounding boxes for detecting faces. Subsequently, Principal Component Analysis was employed to further analyze the data, and attendance was recorded in a database.

III. METHODOLOGY

This proposed method involves the development of an automated attendance system that utilizes facial recognition technology to identify individuals and log their attendance. The system has potential applications in both educational institutions and workplaces where attendance tracking is required. The advantages of this system can be enjoyed by both administrators and stakeholders who are concerned with monitoring attendance. Furthermore, this approach aims to reduce the resources required to maintain accurate attendance records by mitigating the occurrence of human errors, such as fraudulent attendance in academic settings.

A viable solution has been proposed that utilizes a histogram of oriented gradients for the intended application. The proposed system involves the installation of a high-resolution camera at the entrance of the hostel, which will be used to mark attendance. Hostel inmates will be required to scan their faces using this camera to gain entry to the hostel. Additional cameras will be placed inside the hostel premises, positioned in such a way that it can capture the image of every inmate present. All cameras will be equipped with advanced facial recognition technology that will analyse and record attendance based on the faces of the inmates.

The system comprises two distinct roles: Hostel warden and inmates. As per the proposed system, the inmates are required to reach out to the warden to get their face enrolled in the dataset. The warden is responsible for completing a brief form and training the inmate's face. Once this step is completed, the inmate becomes a part of the system and can mark their attendance. The warden, on the other hand, can view an overview of the attendance.

Fig 1: Process Flow

. The entire process is divided into four stages.

1. Creation of A Data Set: To register a new inmate in our system, the warden, who has authorized access, utilizes our software to capture and store the individual's face, which is then linked to their identity. The warden inputs basic information about the inmate via a form and proceeds to train the inmate's face into the system.

2. Training: The dataset generated is fed into our training model, which utilizes a k-NN classifier for image classification. This algorithm is a straightforward form of supervised learning, operating on the premise of similarity between new and existing data. Essentially, the k-NN algorithm identifies the category that bears the closest resemblance to the new case, based on the proximity of available cases. Its underlying assumption is that things with similar features are likely to be located near each other. Thus, k-NN focuses on capturing the notion of similarity, which can be measured in terms of distance or closeness.

3. Face Detection: The system is designed to identify individuals by matching their faces with those stored in the dataset. When an individual requests to mark their attendance, they are required to show their face in front of the camera. The classifier then predicts the identity of the inmate

based on the image captured. If the individual's identity is stored in the dataset, their attendance is marked successfully. However, if their identity is not registered, the system will not be able to recognize them.

4. Attendance Update: The last stage involves recording the individual's presumed identity onto the attendance record, along with the current date and time.

K-Nearest Neighbor Algorithm

The k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN) algorithm is a popular supervised machine learning technique that is often employed for classification and regression tasks. The algorithm operates by identifying the k closest data points in the training dataset to a new data point, and then leveraging the most prevalent class or average value of these k closest neighbors to classify or make predictions about the target variable. In the case of facial recognition-based attendance management systems, the KNN algorithm compares the features of a newly captured image of a face with the pre-existing images stored in the system's database. The algorithm then determines the nearest neighbors to the new image based on the similarity of their features. The accuracy of the model depends on the value of k, which is the number of neighbors used for classification. After the nearest neighbors are identified, the KNN algorithm determines the person's identity in the new image based on the majority class of its neighbors. This information is used to mark the attendance of the identified individual. The KNN algorithm is easy to implement and useful in scenarios where the underlying relationships between features and the target variable are not explicitly known. Although the KNN algorithm is effective in many cases, it can be sensitive to the choice of distance metric and the value of k. Therefore, selecting these parameters carefully is crucial to achieving the desired accuracy level. Overall, the KNN algorithm provides an essential tool for attendance management systems and can be applied to various classification and regression problems. The selection of a suitable distance metric holds significant importance in the K-nearest neighbors (KNN) algorithm. The Euclidean distance metric has gained significant acceptance and conventionally applied in practical scenarios. In the domain of two-dimensional space, the Euclidean distance formula is utilized to ascertain the spatial separation between two points. The present mathematical concept may be articulated as follows: $d = \sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2}$

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#### A function which trains the model on all the faces available in faces folder
def train_model():
    faces = []
    labels = []
    userlist = os.listdir('static/faces')
    for user in userlist:
        for imgname in os.listdir(f'static/faces/{user}'):
            img = cv2.imread(f'static/faces/{user}/{imgname}')
            resized_face = cv2.resize(img, (50, 50))
            faces.append(resized_face.ravel())
            labels.append(user)
    faces = np.array(faces)
    knn = KNeighborsClassifier(n_neighbors=5)
    knn.fit(faces, labels)
    joblib.dump(knn, 'static/face_recognition_model.pkl')
    
```

Fig 2: KNN Algorithm

The k-NN algorithm is versatile and can work well for a wide range of datasets. However, this approach method illustrates certain limitations, namely its vulnerability to extraneous variables and anomalies, as well as its considerable computational complexity when utilized for expansive datasets. The proper selection of a suitable value for 'k' is of utmost significance as it directly affects the accuracy of the algorithm.

Fig 3: Different values of k

Overall, the KNN algorithm provides a simple and effective method for face detection-based attendance management systems, allowing for accurate identification of individuals and tracking of their attendance.

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

The present system features a graphical user interface that is designed to be highly intuitive and easy to use, thereby enabling users of all levels of technical proficiency to interact with the system without requiring advanced technical expertise. Only a fundamental understanding of computing is required. The system is made up of two modules: the Warden module and the Hostel Inmate module. The Hostel Inmate module allows inmates to mark their attendance, while the Warden module enables the warden to train inmates' faces and download attendance sheets

Fig 4: Architecture of the system

In order for inmates to use the system, they must first request the warden to train their faces. Once their faces have been trained, they can continue using the system to mark their

attendance. During the training process, the warden enters the inmate's details, and the camera captures 50 photos of the person until the warden stops the process by pressing 'q' or the escape button. The system then stores the inmate's data in a designated folder.

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Fig 5: User Interface

When marking their attendance, the system captures the inmate's face to display their ID and confirm that their attendance has been marked. The system then updates the attendance in the excel sheet. By implementing this system, the chances of proxy attendance are minimized, and the traditional manual attendance process is streamlined, saving valuable time.

Two Python scripts were created for the purpose of face recognition. The first script is designed to train images using a K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) classifier. The second script is responsible for running the server and identifying a student's face based on the input provided.

Fig 6: Face recognition in real time

Fig 7: Data Set

Fig 8: Attendance being written to a CSV file in real time

The purpose of employing preprocessing stages in a face identification system is to improve its accuracy by reducing false positives and speeding up the detection process. The dataset is stored locally and is used for preprocessing, where Haar cascades frontal face encodings are used. The face detection algorithm utilizes edge or line detection features, which were originally introduced by Viola and Jones in their 2001 research paper "Rapid Object Detection using a Boosted Cascade of Simple Features", to identify faces in images and real-time videos. The algorithm is trained on a vast set of positive photos with faces and a substantial collection of negative images with no faces. In addition to the face detection functionality, two Python codes have been created to support face recognition. One is used for training images with KNN classifier, and the other is used for running the server and recognizing the input student's face. The system's accuracy is 94% when $k=1$, but if the value of k is increased, the accuracy slightly decreases as the search points in the neighborhood increase. However, the implementation of the LBPH algorithm results in a relatively low accuracy of 45%, which is lower than the present algorithm used in this system. The confidence score is evaluated by building test sets and assessing results. Once the feature extraction process is complete, the model is prepared for deployment. During deployment, the model

utilizes real-time video capture to identify the student based on the pre-existing dataset. This process is exemplified in Figure 4. Once the student is identified, their attendance is recorded in a CSV file with their name and timestamp, as depicted in Figure 6.

V. CONCLUSION

The proposed system is designed to provide a more effective alternative for maintaining attendance records in educational institutions and organizations. It seeks to solve the drawbacks of traditional attendance systems, such as time-consuming processes, paper and ink waste, and proxy attendance concerns. Although the focus of this system is on managing attendance records for hostel inmates, it can be adapted and improved for larger organizations, such as multinational corporations, that require a more efficient and effective way of keeping track of attendance records. The system being proposed has the capacity to handle a considerable amount of attendance records, making it a practical solution for managing attendance in educational institutions and organizations. By using this system, these institutions and organizations can streamline their attendance management process, thereby saving time, effort, and resources.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] K. Puthea, R. Hartanto and R. Hidayat, "A review paper on attendance marking system based on face recognition," 2017 2nd International conferences on Information Technology, Information Systems and Electrical Engineering (ICITISEE), 2017, pp. 304-309, doi: 10.1109/ICITISEE.2017.8285517.
- [2] Vishwas K V , Abhishek V Tatachar, Dheeraj D "An Automated Attendance System Based on the Concept of Histogram of Oriented Gradients", MATJournals, <http://dx.doi.org/10.46610/JOIPAI.2020.v06i03.003>
- [3] E. Rekha and P. Ramaprasad, "An efficient automated attendance management system based on Eigen Face recognition," 2017 7th International Conference on Cloud Computing, Data Science & Engineering - Confluence, 2017, pp.605-608, doi: 10.1109/CONFLUENCE.2017.7943223.
- [4] A. Raghuvanshi and P. D. Swami, "An automated classroom attendance system using video based face recognition," 2017 2nd IEEE International Conference on Recent Trends in Electronics, Information & Communication Technology (RTEICT), 2017, pp. 719-724, doi: 10.1109/RTEICT.2017.8256691.
- [5] Khan, S., Akram, A. & Usman, N. "Real Time Automatic Attendance System for Face Recognition Using Face API and OpenCV." Wireless Pers Commun 113, 469-480 (2020) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11277-020-07224-2>.
- [6] Amrutha H. B, Anitha C, Channanjamurthy K, N, Raghu R, 2018, "Attendance Monitoring System Using Face Recognition," INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY (IJERT) NCESC - 2018 (Volume 6 - Issue 13)
- [7] B. Tej Chinimilli, A. T., A. Kotturi, V. Reddy Kaipu and J. Varma Mandapati, "Face Recognition based Attendance System using Haar Cascade and Local Binary Pattern Histogram Algorithm," 2020 4th International Conference on Trends in Electronics and Informatics (ICOEI)(48184), 2020, pp. 701-704, doi: 10.1109/ICOEI48184.2020.9143046.
- [8] S. Sawhney, K. Kacker, S. Jain, S. N. Singh and R. Garg, "Real-Time Smart Attendance System using Face Recognition Techniques," 2019 9th International Conference on Cloud Computing, Data Science & Engineering (Confluence), 2019, pp. 522-525, doi: 10.1109/CONFLUENCE.2019.8776934.